

THE IMPORTANCE OF GULKHANI'S WORK ZARBULMASAL IN THE LITERATURE

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Abstract

This article provides valuable information about Zarbulmasal, an artistic work, written in the 19th century by Muhammadsharifzoda Gulkhani. “Zarbulmasal” is the greatest work that shows how uzbek generations lived and what kind of difficulties they had to face and in what ways they could overcome all them. Readers can realize the importance of this work only after comprehending this article.

Key words: prose, storytelling, metophor, proverbs, masterpiece, Yaparaloqqush, Boyugli, Monkey and najjor

Аннотация

В данной статье представлена ценная информация о художественном произведении «Зарбулмасал», написанном в XIX веке Мухаммадшарифзода Гюльханий. «Зарбулмасал» – величайшее произведение, которое показывает, как жили поколения узбеков, с какими трудностями им приходилось сталкиваться и какими способами они могли их все преодолеть. Читатели смогут ос

ознать важность данной работы только после прочтения данной статьи.

Ключевые слова: проза, повествование, метафора, пословицы, шедевр, Япалоккуш, Бобюгли, Обезьяна и наджор.

Introduction

There were many great poets who demonstrated the emotions towards the life and the people around them. However, Only some of them had a special talent to create such a beautiful and meaningful prose like Zarbulmasal. In addition of “zarb” and “masal” come from arabian language meaning “speaking by using proverbs”. Gulkhani whose real name was decided to write this masterpiece on the order of Khan of the Kokand, that is to say, Umar Khan. Gulkhani had worked for a long time and included about 400 uzbek proverbs and so much useful advice. Besides utilizing proverbs professionally, the poet also showed the lifestyles of the nation of those times metaphorically. Before Muhammadsharifzoda, there were some writers such as Ubayd Zokoni, Nozil Xo’jandi, Sulaymonqul Ruji wrote Zarbulmasals. However, our great poet Gulkhani’s Zarbulmasal much different than those ones., because Muhammadsharifzoda Gulkhani created his work on the basis of storytelling. His metaphoric styles, for instance, making the birds speak and discuss like real people. The noticeable poet was able to put human beings’ characters onto the birds. Apart from this, he also added little stories which can give motivation or lessons for the people, thereby his work can be similar to Kalila and Dimna (one of masterpieces of East culture). That is why, taking a look at his work once, one can easily discover how knowledgeable person was Gulkhani since you cannot write such a valuable work if you do not have enough knowledge about the lives of ordinary people. According to Fazli from his early age, he worked so hard. The time when he started working as a fire extinguisher he took nickname of Gulkhani (symbolizing flame) which is well-known for everyone today. The author of Majmuai Shoiron Fazliy claimed that Muhammadsharif’s nicknames

said all about his behaviour. Gulkhani was very passionate about truth and his heart was like fuel to honesty.

Methodology

There were many scientists who studied Gulkhani's life and his works for many years. Researches showed that all his poems, ghazals and Zarbulmasal are based on his attitudes towards the social problems of his time. At that time, Umar Khan paid a great attention to collect all literary experts and other talented people around his him. Besides Gulkhani, noticeable artists including Yori, Zavqi, Nizami, Makhmur, Nadira, Uvaisi, Mushrif, Fazli namangani were helped and patronized by Amir Umar Khan.

Literary scholar E.Shodiyev, when he demonstrates the site of events in Zarbulmasal's work, was not sure whether Gulkhani meant the ruins of this Shahrستان.2. But in this work, it is written that this place is "in the climate of Fergana". The area around Uratapa is also considered to be part of the Fergana climate, but given the fact that the play "Fergana State" (Kokand Khanate) is meant by the combination "Fergana Climate", it is necessary to change this opinion

Results

Gulkhani, a great poet of Uzbek literature, was born in one of the small villages of Kokand at the end of 18 th century and died in 19 th..There were not a plenty of information the personal life of the poet. The author of "Majmuai Shoiron" Fazli namangani said he was he was from Kokand, however, Vazi ("Tuxfat ul-ahbob") wrote that Gulkhani came from Namangan. In Kokand, Gulkhani tried himself in many professions including a fire maker and soldier. The famous poet and writer Gulkhani was always a person who has a sharp pen (meaning good at expressing his emotions by writing). He could oppose the unfaith only expressing his feelings in his poems

As a proof of statement, take a look at his poem called "Bideh".

Dying from hunger give me a piece of bread my lord,
 Give me please bahmon so as not to die like enemy
 Wheat, rice and green beans please, - that's all I want
 I never ever ask you any diamond or else jewelry

As you realized by looking through the poem, the author professionally moved his emotions and the feelings of other soldiers like him to this poem. He wrote 12 ghazals, 1 ode, and “Zarbulmasal” that reached us. Zarbulmasal is all about deep morality and education. **The ideological direction of the work is very clear in the expressions, which were given during the presentation of the bold for Boyoglu's daughter. In the political rivalry between the two khans, Gulkhani wants to show the superiority of his khanate and discriminate against the opposition. It turns out that the main idea of the work is not to show and expose corruption, but to be proud of the prosperity and victory of their country and the idea of patriotism.**

Discussions

Gulkhani's approach and remarks are ironic and deceptive, in effect denouncing the destructive policies of his khanate. As in the whole content of the work, of course, in this case, too, the writer may have meant irony and evasion. However, the most important aspect of this issue is that Gulkhani, no matter how progressive he was, was first and foremost man of his time - the era of khanates, a citizen of the Kokand khanate. Like his contemporaries and compatriots, he rejoiced in the success of the Kokand khan and khanate, and the narrow sense of patriotism created by the historical situation was not alien to him. By depicting the villages of Bukhara in ruins, the author not only exposes the Bukhara Khanate for that period, but also gives a broad and clear picture of the sociopolitical landscape of the historical period for the next generation.

Conclusions

Ultimately, Gulkhaniy's Zarbulmasal place a crucial role in literature.As

a poet, Gulkhani collected about 400 proverbs and connected them with the story of birds. In the play, birds talk, have an argument, discuss which means they have all the behaviours of people. Even the story seems a little bit like comedy it has a deep meaning. Gulkhani tried to describe the events that were happening in Movorounnahr at that time. For instance, the arguments between character Boyogli and Yapalloqqush is like political rivalry between his khanate and his rivals. In some ways, the author exposes corruption when tKorqush as a matchmaker offers giving some places to Boyogli to give his daughter to Yapaloqqush's son. Furthermore, Gulkhani did not forget to show how much he was proud of his country. He talks about the victories of his khanate and the wonderful sites of Movorounnahr. His remarks and methods are quite deceptive and ironic. Without this work, readers will not understand the details of the period of khanates. Zarbulmasal is not only essential but also is an intangible heritage for generations. The proverbs shown in the play, are considered as the forms of folk literature. They depict the wisdom of people in ancient times.

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